

Introduction

One of the most prevalent illnesses is deep vein thrombosis, which can lead to pulmonary embolism and post-thrombotic syndrome. A thrombus can form on its own or as a result of clinical situations such as surgery, trauma, or prolonged bed rest. Prophylaxis with low-dose anticoagulation is successful in these cases. Imaging techniques such as ultrasonography or venography are used to diagnose deep vein thrombosis. A thrombus is found in roughly 25% of symptomatic patients. To rule out deep vein thrombosis, clinical risk assessment and D-dimer assay are utilized. Low-molecular-weight heparin, followed by vitamin K antagonists, can reduce thrombus development and embolization.

Blood clots in the deep veins of the legs are prevented by intermittent pneumatic compression (IPC) devices. The devices work by squeezing your legs with cuffs that fill with air. This helps avoid blood clots by increasing blood flow through the veins of your legs. The small valves in your legs' veins keep blood going back up toward your heart. A DVT, on the other hand, may damage one or more of these valves. They get weakened or leaky as a result of this. Blood starts to pool in your legs when this happens. If you are sedentary for an extended period of time, this can also happen. When the muscles in the leg contract, blood normally moves up into the veins. When blood flows slowly through the veins, the danger of blood cells sticking together and forming a clot increases. Your calf or entire leg is cuffed when wearing an IPC device. Like a blood pressure cuff, the cuff fills with air and squeezes the leg. The cuff deflates and relaxes after that. The procedure then continues indefinitely. The compression aids in the circulation of blood via your veins to your heart. IPC also encourages your body's natural release of anti-clotting chemicals. The device's cuffs loosen between compressions, allowing oxygen-rich blood to continue to flow into your leg's arteries.

Methodology

Intermittent pneumatic compression is a treatment approach that uses an air pump and inflatable auxiliary sleeves, gloves, or boots in a system to enhance venous circulation in the limbs of patients who have edema or are at risk of DVT or pulmonary embolism (PE). In use, the limb requiring treatment is encased in an inflated jacket (sleeve, glove, pants, or boot), and pressure lines are linked between the jacket and the air pump. When the pump is turned on, it fills the air chambers in the jacket, pressurizing the tissues in the limb and driving fluids like blood and lymph out of the pressurized area. The pressure is removed after a short time, enabling increasing blood flow back into the leg.

The device's principal function is to "squeeze blood from the underlying deep veins, which will be shifted proximally providing that the valves are competent." The veins will refill with blood as the inflatable sleeves deflate. The sleeves' intermittent compressions will ensure venous blood mobility.

Figure 1 DVT pump

Sequential compression devices,

SCDs are sleeves with distinct zones or pockets of inflation that work to squeeze the appendage in a "milking action." The most distal portions will expand first, and then the adjacent pockets will do the same.

In neurosurgery, the primary prophylactic for preventing DVT and pulmonary embolism is sequential calf compression and graduated compression stockings, sometimes in combination with low molecular weight heparins or unfractionated heparin.

During lengthy laparoscopic surgery, intraoperative SCD therapy is advised to counteract decreased venous blood return from the lower extremities and the resulting cardiac depression produced by pneumoperitoneum (inflation of the abdomen with carbon dioxide)

Is sequential compression better than uniform compression?

Multiple bladders are used to compress the leg in a "milking" motion in graduated or graded sequential compression. The cuffs are arranged in order, with the most distal bladder inflating first and the most proximal bladder inflating last, and they are graded, with the most distal bladder inflating to the highest pressure and the most proximal bladder inflating to the lowest. The cuffs were created after extensive laboratory research into fluid flow revealed that they would be more effective at emptying a limb.

Figure 2

Image 2 shows a typical velocity profile from such a system, where different bladders (their inflations labeled in the figure) cause individual peaks in the augmentation, thereby spreading out the augmentation over a lengthy period of time. However, the peak velocities produced by such systems are usually no higher than those produced by simpler uniform compression, as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3

FIGURE 2: Venous blood flow velocity in the posterior tibial vein when a foot cuff is applied (velocity [cm/s] vs. time [1 second per vertical dotted line]). Figure 3: Venous blood flow velocity in the femoral vein when a foot cuff is applied (velocity [cm/s] vs. time [1 second per vertical dotted line]).

The location of the velocity measurement is critical since the blood flow velocity in a vein is determined by the vein's diameter. The common femoral vein is roughly 16 mm in diameter, the popliteal vein is 8 mm, and the posterior tibial vein is 4 mm in diameter under typical circumstances. As a result, for a given amount of blood ejected from the foot, the velocities reached in the posterior tibial vein should be higher than in the femoral vein. Because the plantar venous plexus in the foot holds a lesser volume of blood than the calf

and thigh, the velocity must also depend on which region of the leg is compressed. The velocity properties of different amounts of blood propelled via the same blood artery should be expected to differ.

All intermittent compression methods, according to reports, cause alterations in femoral vein velocity. Highest velocities reached with calf and/or thigh compression at pressures around 40 mm Hg would be 35–60 cm/s^{11–13}, with augmentations (maximum velocity during compression compared to maximum velocity resting) of roughly 50–250 percent. Popliteal velocities are around 55 cm/s. Peak velocities of >100 cm/s have been recorded in both the popliteal and femoral veins at pressures of 120 mm Hg, as well as a system that rapidly inflates to 80 mm Hg before dropping to "normal" values. Foot compression has generated modest results, typically 20–40 cm/s in the femoral vein, with slightly higher rates (30–55 cm/s) in the popliteal vein, as expected. In one case, the velocity of the posterior tibial vein was more than twice that of the popliteal vein. However, it should always be remembered that venous blood flow varies. Resting blood flow in the femoral vein varies not just from one person to the next, but also over time due to natural oscillations in the input to the leg. The flow pattern will alter depending on the individual's physiology and current body position, with breathing and the cardiac cycle affecting the flow to varying degrees. Furthermore, because venous blood pressure changes over time, the reproducibility of velocity data from a certain pump in a specific individual will not be flawless.

Reference

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